

AN EFFECTIVE BEGINNING READING METHOD IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' UNDERSTANDING OF SUBJECTS INDONESIAN LANGUAGE OF CLASS 1 AT UPT SDN 3 WAY KENANGA WEST TULANG BAWANG REGENCY

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Abstract: The aim of the research is to find the right method to use in teaching beginning reading skills to grade 1 students at SDN 3 Way Kenanga. The aim of beginning reading is also explained in (Depdikbud, 1994:4), namely so that "Students can read simple words and sentences fluently and precisely". The classroom action research (PTK) method was used in this research. The subjects of this research were grade 1 students at SDN 3 Way Kenanga with a total of 27 students consisting of 14 female students and 13 male students. The results of this research are that the syllable method applied in class I at SDN 3 Way Kenanga can actually improve students' initial reading skills. Beginning reading skills can be seen from the average grade in the class which shows an increase from cycle I to cycle II. Observations show that with the implementation of classroom actions in this study almost all students can read simple words, simple sentences and words with consonants. duplicate well and correctly. This can be seen from the average value of 70.92. Before the learning process in the classroom, the teacher should first know the condition of the students and the conditions in the classroom so that they can find out the right method to apply well. Apart from that, teachers are advised to identify the desires and expectations of their students so that they are able to plan appropriate methods to be used in the learning process so that learning objectives can be achieved easily

Keywords: Beginning Reading Method, Comprehension, Indonesian.

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Introduction

The Indonesian government has established regulations through the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 13 of 2007 concerning School Principal Standards. Creating quality school principals is one of the government's programs in managing educational institutions in Indonesia, namely in facing demands for quality improvement. Quality problems have many problems related to standards and quality measurements themselves, for this reason school

principals must have a reliable quality management concept in managing quality education (Azmi & Ridha, 2019). There are three aspects that must be fulfilled to create qualified human resources, namely basic literacy, character and competency. Literacy skills are key in the learning process. Ideally, literacy in lower grades should be varied to avoid student boredom and boredom. In lower grades, children's reading development must be considered because it can influence children's reading fluency and increase their information and knowledge (Kemendikbud, 2021).

Reading is divided into two stages, namely initial reading and advanced reading. Beginning reading is the stage of the process of learning to read for elementary school students in class I and class II, while advanced reading is the process of learning to read for elementary school students in class III, IV, V and VI (Dewi & Pertiwi, 2019). In essence, reading activities consist of two parts, namely reading as a process and reading as a product. Reading as a process is initial reading for first and second grade because it contains the initial learning process of getting to know the science of reading.

Reading as a product is advanced reading and is used for grades three to grade 6 because at this level children can read and will be able to receive the results of what they read. For grade 1 elementary school students, reading is the most important part of the process of seeking knowledge. (Sumarni, et.al) stated that students who cannot read well will experience difficulties in participating in learning activities for all subjects. Therefore, teachers must be innovative and creative in order to increase students' understanding and enthusiasm for learning. According to Ningrum (2018), beginning reading is an important skill for students to master from an early age, because it is a very valuable provision in learning activities, especially learning activities at the next level. Anderson (in Ningrum, 2018) also said that student success in learning activities lies in the student's ability to translate written language symbols which can be achieved through initial reading skills taught from the lower grade level.

Nurhadi (2016) revealed that one of the goals of someone carrying out reading activities is to get information from something written through written symbols. Thus, initial reading must be carried out as much as possible for grade 1 students. Based on observations and interviews as well as classroom action research (PTK) conducted by researchers at SDN 03 Way Kenanga, Way Kenanga District, West Tulang Bawang Regency through several cycles, namely pre-cycle, cycle one and cycle two explains that initial reading activities should use appropriate methods and are appropriate to the students' circumstances. on May 20 2024, the results showed that the reading ability of class I students was still low because many could not read, apart from that the students were unable to combine letters into syllables, words and sentences. Then during learning, students are less focused on learning because students are busy playing. Apart from that, in the learning process teachers still use conventional methods such as lectures and spelling methods, which makes students less active in learning and makes the teaching and learning process often patterned in one direction only.

In the 21st century, teachers can utilize technology in carrying out learning to make it easier for students and greatly facilitate students to develop themselves and their potential. Technology is knowledge that is transformed into products, processes, services and organizational structures (Rusman, et al. 2015:78). In initial reading learning, teachers can use learning media in the form of sentence cards, word cards, syllable cards, letter cards and can also use phonemes and use objects

around the class that can support students' understanding . According to (Sadiman 2015:83) Media is something that is useful as a messenger. Learning media can stimulate students' thoughts, attention, feelings and interest in the learning process. On this occasion the researcher took the title " Effective initial reading method in improving students' understanding in class 1 Indonesian Language Lessons at UPT SD 3 way cananga" The aim of this research is: (1) to describe the reading method for lower classes (2) to find out the factors which affects the initial reading ability of class I students at SDN 3 way cananga with problem formulation (1) what difficulties are experienced by class 1 students in the initial reading process (2) what methods can be used in the initial reading process.

Methods

The research was carried out in class 1 of SDN 3 Way Kenanga. The subjects of this research were grade 1 students at SDN 3 Way Kenanga with a total of 27 students consisting of 14 female students and 13 male students. The research procedure used is the classroom action research (PTK) method. Classroom action research is action research carried out by a teacher who also acts as a researcher in his class or can also collaborate with other people by designing, implementing and reflecting on actions collaboratively and participatively. Which consists of several cycles of four stages that must be gone through: Planning, implementation, observation, evaluation and reflection. Aims to improve and increase the quality of learning in the class through actions taken. Some of the reasons the author uses PTK is to further improve the learning process.

The advantages of PTK stated by Shumsky are: (1) Collaboration in PTK creates a sense of mutual belonging, (2) Collaboration in PTK encourages creativity and critical thinking, in this case teachers as well as researchers, (3) Collaboration in PTK produces change positive, (4) Cooperation in PTK increases agreement in resolving the problems faced. The data collection techniques used in this research are: Daily Notes, Observation, interviews, Field Notes, Documentation. In data processing, taking data from daily values and values taken as pre-cycle values. Describe the data found in detail, then draw conclusions from the description or results of the actions that have been taken.

There are two data assessed in this research, namely data on students' reading development activities and learning outcomes. These two data are processed by looking for the percentage. Analysis of student learning outcomes. Student completion percentage = $\frac{\text{student scores}}{\text{maximum score}} \times 100\%$. To determine students' abilities in learning, data that researchers have obtained during the learning process can be taken. Indicators of performance success in this research are determined as follows:

1. Mastery of reading methods in learning Indonesian using the application of the syllable method for grade 1 students at SDN 03 Way Kenanga is said to improve if their qualifications are in the good category or with a score as low as 65.

2. The results of the research show that the use of the syllable method in learning Indonesian can improve reading skills in grade 1 students at SDN 03 Way Kenanga. This will be achieved if aspects of reading skills show improved results from cycle I to cycle 2.

Table 1
Assessment Aspects

No	Rated aspect	Score
1	Introduction to letters of the alphabet	25
2	Word combination	25
3	Correct intonation	30
4	Read long sentences	20
Amount		100

Results and Discussion

SDN 3 Way Kenanga is one of the elementary schools in Way Kenanga sub-district, West Bone Regency, Lampung. which has 391 students whose learning uses two curricula, namely the K13 curriculum and the Merdeka curriculum. The K13 curriculum is used by students in grades 3 and 6, while the independent curriculum is used in grades 1, 2, 4 and 5. Before carrying out the research process, the researcher first carried out teaching and learning activities with the aim of finding out the real conditions in the field and the existing problems. . The strategy used in this research is problems that arise in the classroom, especially in the process of learning Indonesian language material. This research focuses more on the problems that occur in class I of SDN 3 Way Kenanga related to the low initial reading skills of students in that class. Of the 27 students, there were still 5 students who got scores below the KKM (<75) or 76.3% who were not yet fluent in reading. Even though the Minimum Completeness Criteria limit score for Indonesian language lessons is 65. Apart from the student score data. Researchers tried to use several methods, namely:

Spell Method

The spelling method is a reading method by saying the sound of letters. The approach used in the spelling method is a literal approach. Beginning Reading Learning with this method begins the teaching by introducing letters alphabetically. Students pronounce these letters according to their sound according to the alphabet. After this stage, students are invited to get acquainted with syllables by combining several letters that they already know. For example: b, a – ba (read be.a – ba) c, a – ca (read ce.a – ca) ba-ca is pronounced read b, u, k, u becomes bu – bu (pronounced be.u – bu) ku – ku (pronounced ka.u – ku) This process is the same as initial reading, after children can read the letters loose letters, then continue with learning to read a series of letters in the form of syllables. The next

learning stage is the introduction of simple sentences. Provide examples of combining letters into syllables, syllables into words, and words into sentences. In selecting reading and writing teaching materials, the beginning should start from concrete things to abstract things, from things that are easy, familiar, familiar to the child's life to those that are difficult and may be something new for the child.

Sound and Alphabet Method

sound method is a method of early reading learning by voicing consonant letters assisted by vowels (a, I, u, e, o). In traditional grammar, consonant letters are called consonants. For example, the consonant letter b is pronounced eb/be, the letter d is pronounced ed/de, so this method is done by spelling and this method can also be called the spelling method. The advantage of this method is that students recognize the level of the simplest forms of language. Students can memorize the sounds of the letters in the alphabet of the language being studied.

Meanwhile, the weakness of this method is that students have difficulty finding new letters because they are used to memorizing. Students have difficulty pronouncing diphthongs. The sound method is almost the same as the spelling method, the difference lies in the alphabet or letter pronunciation system. For example: the letter b is pronounced /beh/ d is pronounced /deh/ c is pronounced /ceh/ g is pronounced /geh/ p is pronounced /peh/ and so on. Thus the word "cow" is spelled: Es.a – sa Ep.i – pi – pronounced – sa-pi. This method is part of the spelling method. The basic principles of the learning process are not much different from the spelling/alphabet method. The difference only lies in the way or system of reading (pronunciation) of the alphabet. The difference between the alphabetic method is that letters are pronounced as alphabets, whereas in the sound method letters are pronounced as sounds

Syllable Method and Word Method

method is a method that requires students to master syllables first in order to read a word. This method tends to combine syllables with other syllables. And for the initial stages, use hyphens to make it easier for children to understand. The initial reading learning process with this method begins with the introduction of syllables. Syllables are strung together to form meaningful words. For example, from a list of syllables the teacher can make various variations of syllables into meaningful words, for teaching materials for beginning reading and writing, for example: b, a, j, u become b, a → ba (spelled /be-a/ → [ba]) j, u → ju (spelled /je-u/ → [ju]) ba-ju → pronounced /baju/ b, u, k, u, becomes b, u → bu (spelled /be-u / → [bu]) bu-ku → pronounced /buku/ This activity can be continued with the process of arranging words into simple sentences.

Global Method

The global method is a method that uses teaching materials for initial reading and writing by
 (1) Introducing pictures and sentences (2) Decomposing one of the sentences into words; words

become syllables; syllables become letters. For example: this is budi, how to read this, bu-di, then separate the vocabulary into a word, this- budi

SAS Method (Synthetic Analytical Structural)

The SAS method is a story approach accompanied by pictures . When choosing an interesting method, teachers must pay attention to the students' personalities so that learning goes well. The advantage of the SAS method is that it makes it easy for children to follow procedures and will be able to read quickly the next time. Based on linguistic grounds, this method will help children. master reading fluently. The disadvantage of the SAS method is that the teacher must be creative, skilled and patient. This kind of demand is considered very difficult for the current condition of teachers, many facilities that must be prepared to implement this method for certain schools are considered difficult, the SAS method is only for learning consumers in urban areas and not in rural areas. Because it is quite difficult to teach teachers the SAS method.

Peel Chain Method

The peel-off method is a method that is implemented by the teacher introducing the letters of the alphabet first, then arranging the syllables to form letters and connecting the letters to form syllables.

For example: my books my books

Appropriate method to support the understanding of reading learning for grade 1 students at SDN 3 Way Kenanga is the sound method and collaboration with the global method. The aim of this collaboration is for students to memorize the letters of the alphabet first and then use global methods to improve students' reading fluency. Pre-cycle activities were carried out by interviewing Mrs. Oliv as class 1 teacher and Mr. BUDI SETIO S.Ag as the principal of SDN 3 Way Kenanga. In cycle one, the syllable method shows that there is an increase in the quality of learning. Of the total 1st grade students, there are 27 children, consisting of 13 male students and 14 female students. There are 10 children who are not yet proficient in reading, 5 of them do not know the letters of the alphabet, either vowels or consonants, so they cannot combine syllables into complete sentences, while 4 of them can already recognize letters, can read short sentences, but cannot read long sentences. The following is a table of research results in class 1 of SDN 3 Way Kenanga on Monday 20 May 2024

Table 2
Obtaining Student Ability Scores in Reading
Using the Syllable Method in Cycle 1

No	Category	Score range	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very good	5	7	25.9%
2.	Pretty good	3	15	55.5%
3.	Very less	1	5	18.5%
	Amount	-	27	100

In cycle two the researchers used the alphabet method and the global method and there was an increase in the number of students who could read as many as 20 students. 4 students could not read because they had not memorized the letters, 3 of them could not combine syllables. The following is a table of cycle two activities.

Table 3
Obtaining Student Ability Scores in Reading
Using the Syllable Method in Cycle II

No	Category	Score range	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very good	5	20	74%
2	Pretty good	3	3	11.1%
3	Very less	1	4	14.8%
			27	

Students' difficulties in completing assignments were measured using a reading simulation in front of the class one by one. Based on the results of the analysis of each student's scores, the researchers concluded that the difficulties experienced by students were in combining long syllables and long sentences as well as reading new sentences. However, initial reading skills in elementary school grade 1 use the alphabet method and global method increased amounting to 36.73%. This is evidence of the influence of the application of the alphabet method and global method on learning initial reading skills.

So, Indonesian language lessons have several skills. These include reading and writing skills. Results of research data from the "Indonesian *National Assessment Program* " held by the Ministry of Education and Culture in 2019. This research aims to examine the extent to which the percentage of students' reading ability, mathematics ability and science ability states that only 6.06% of Indonesian students already have good reading skills, while the remaining 47.11% are in the sufficient category and 46.83% have poor reading skills (Kemdikbud, 2019). This means that Indonesian students' reading ability is still very poor.

activities in educational units are dominated by reading activities. Early reading is the beginning of a child's entry into elementary school . At the beginning of reading, it will illustrate the process of fluency (correct language pronunciation) (Brown Carmin Sherry, 2018). There are also aspects that a child must have in conveying them, including knowing letters, fluency, knowing spelling, and understanding reading (Government, 2017). This is a must have, if you don't have this aspect a child will find it difficult to follow it. This opinion was also expressed by (Peng, 2019) stating that this aspect is very mandatory to master as the basis for its delivery.

Conclusion

Beginning reading or process reading is the process of learning to read for early grade elementary school students. The goal is for students to have the ability to understand and interpret writing, as a basis for being able to read further. Methods used in teaching reading in class 1. Based on the results and discussions presented in the previous discussion, it can be concluded that. The initial reading ability of class I students at SDN 3 Way Kenanga in the 2023/2024 academic year is included in the sufficient category. Some aspects of beginning reading have not been mastered optimally by students. The highest percentage of initial reading ability aspects is the pronunciation aspect at 35.32%. The lowest percentage of initial reading ability is the self-confidence aspect of 17.75%. There are 7 students with a percentage of 26.15% who are in the very good category, 11 students with a percentage of 42, 28% are in the good category, 4 students with a percentage of 13.34% are in the fair category, and 8 students with a percentage of 28.23% are in the poor category.

Factors that influence the initial reading ability of class I students at SDN 3 Way Kenanga are 1). Environmental factors, including learning experiences and environmental conditions. This factor is the most dominant factor influencing initial reading ability. Parents do not provide maximum learning assistance at home to students to be able to hone their reading skills because they are busy working, so students have less experience with reading skills. 2). Psychological factors, including motivation and interest in reading. Students who fall into the very good and good categories have high learning motivation and interest in reading, so they have good reading skills, because students get used to reading every day, while students who fall into the poor category have less motivation to learn because prefer to play rather than practice reading texts to improve reading skills. 3). Intellectual factors include students' abilities or intelligence in mastering something taught. Each student has a different reading ability category because each student has a different level of intelligence.

Students who fall into the very good reading category basically have a good level of intelligence so they are faster in mastering reading skills. Vice versa. Apart from that, the factors that influence students' initial reading abilities also lie with the teacher. The teacher's lack of creativity makes students less likely to enjoy reading lessons because they only use the same methods. It is hoped that teachers can change reading methods to methods that are easier to understand. student.

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